

Mobilegap Magyarország Zrt.
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MQTT Simulator
Software Documentation

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Funding summary

The company was awarded **HUF 115,687,392** in funding for its project titled "*Development of a Next-Generation Corporate Service Platform*", submitted under the call for proposals "*Support for R&D&I Activities of Enterprises*", within the framework of the **Economic Development and Innovation Operational Program (GINOP)**, with the identification number **GINOP-2.1.2-8-1-4-16-2017-00240**. The total value of the project was **HUF 231,381,140**, and it was implemented by the **Zrt.** between **March 1, 2019, and May 29, 2021**.

Introduction

MQTT (MQ Telemetry Transport) is a network-based message transmission protocol, in which endpoints participating in communication can subscribe to topics and send messages to these topics. Endpoints can subscribe to an arbitrary number of topics. If a message is received on a given topic, all endpoints subscribed to that topic will receive the message. The subscription and message forwarding associated with the topic are managed by the MQTT broker.

The MQTT simulator is a utility that allows the examination of communication and data traffic between an MQTT broker and multiple MQTT clients.

Objectives

The simulator aims to analyze the communication between MQTT clients and test the functionality of the broker module.

Required Software

Installed Programs:

- Windows operating system
- Web browser (e.g., Firefox, Google Chrome)
- Node.js (v10.16.3) + npm - link
- MQTT broker: e.g., EMQ X (v3.2.1) - link or Mosquitto - link
- MQTT.js (v3.0.0) - link

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- Notepad++ (for display and development) - link

Included Files:

For the First Version:

- index.html
- Simulator.js

For the Second Version:

- index2.html
 - Clients.json
 - Client_templates.json
 - Simulator2.js
 - ListenerServer.js
-

Starting the EMQ X Broker

The broker can be started from the console using the following command:

```
./bin/emqx start
```

The bin folder is located in the broker's directory.

(If port configuration is required, the HTTP Listener is available in the etc\plugins\emqx_management.conf file.)

After this, the broker's control module can be accessed in a web browser on the local machine at the following address:

```
http://127.0.0.1:18083
```

Default login credentials:

- **Username:** admin

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- **Password:** public

Figure 1: Control Panel Interface

In the "Monitoring" section of the control panel, information about connected endpoints, topics, subscriptions, and data Broker traffic can be retrieved. In the "Rule Engine" section, rules and filtering conditions can be configured for messages.

The broker can be stopped with the following command:

```
./bin/emqx stop
```

Starting the Simulation

The included files should be placed in the same directory where MQTT.js is installed.

First Version

Run Simulator.js from the console (in the second case, outputs will be written to the specified file):


```
>node Simulator.js
```

 or

```
>node Simulator.js > MyLog.txt
```

After this, the simulator interface can be accessed at:

Figure 2: Simulator Interface

First, specify the number of clients, then click the "Create clients" button. This will generate the specified number of clients. Next, the number of topics must be set, and clicking the "Subscribe clients" button will randomly subscribe the clients to topics. Finally, set the event frequency and click "Start". During the simulation, an event occurs at the specified interval where a randomly selected client sends a message to a randomly selected topic.

The simulation can be stopped by clicking the "End" button.

Example Input:

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Figure 3: Example Input

Depending on the execution method, the simulation results can be tracked in the console or in the specified file, showing which topic received a message, its content, and which clients were subscribed to that topic:

Figure 4: Console Output

Second Version

Run Simulator2.js from the console:

```
>node Simulator2.js
```

or

```
>node Simulator2.js > MyLog.txt
```

After this, the simulator interface can be accessed at:

Figure 5: Simulator v2 Interface

On the simulator interface, first, import the clients defined in the Clients.json file using the "Import clients" button.

Next, fill in the "Broker url", "Port", and "Output" fields. The "Output" field specifies the file where data will be written during the simulation. If the file does not exist, it will be created automatically in the simulator directory. If the same file is used for multiple simulations, its contents will be overwritten, and only the results of the last simulation will be visible. After entering the data, click "Set simulation" to apply the values to the clients, connect them to the specified broker, and configure the output file.

The simulation starts with the "Start simulation" button, and results will be written to the specified file.

To stop the simulation, click the "End simulation" button. The generated data can be found in the specified file.

To finalize the simulation, click the "Finish" button, which will disconnect the clients from the broker.

Clients can be defined in the Clients.json file as follows:

```
{
  "Clients": [
    {
      "Name": "Number Generator",
      "Topics": ["Generated Value"],
      "Subscribe": [],
      "MessageType": "JSON",
      "Message": "{Number1: @, Number2: @}",
      "DataValue": [ [-2, 2], [0, 10] ],
      "Interval": 5
    },
    {
      "Name": "Text Generator",
      "Topics": ["Generated Value"],
      "Subscribe": [],
      "MessageType": "JSON",
      "Message": "{Text: @}",
      "DataValue": [ ["ON", "OFF"] ],
      "Interval": 5
    },
    {
      "Name": "Number & Text Generator",
      "Topics": ["Mix Generated Values"],
      "Subscribe": [],
      "MessageType": "JSON",
      "Message": "{Number: @, Text: @}",
      "DataValue": [ [0, 10], ["ON", "OFF", "STANDBY"] ],
      "Interval": 5
    },
    {
      "Name": "Data Viewer",
      "Topics": [],
      "Subscribe": ["Generated Value", "Mix Generated Values"],
      "MessageType": "",
      "Message": "",
      "DataValue": [],
      "Interval": 0
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 6: Defining Clients

- **Name:** The client's name.
- **Topics:** Topics to which the client sends messages.
- **Subscribe:** Topics to which the client subscribes.
- **Message and DataValue:** The '@' characters in the message are replaced with randomly selected values within the ranges specified in the DataValue field. The number of '@' characters in the message must match the number of ranges in the DataValue field. (Multiple ranges can be defined as follows: [[0, 10], [11, 20]])
- **Interval:** The time interval at which the client generates messages.

Messages can be tracked in the specified output file:

```
C:\Windows\system32\cmd.exe
[5.006] SEND
<Number Generator> client sends message to topic
Generated Value:
"{Number1: 0, Number2: 4}"

[5.011] SEND
<Text Generator> client sends message to topic
Generated Value:
"{Text: ON}"

[5.011] SEND
<Number & Text Generator> client sends message to topic
Mix Generated Values:
"{Number: 0, Text: OFF}"

[5.013] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Generated Value:
"{Text: ON}"

[5.014] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Generated Value:
"{Number1: 0, Number2: 4}"

[5.015] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Mix Generated Values:
"{Number: 0, Text: OFF}"
```

```
[5.007] SEND
<Number Generator> client sends message to topic
Generated Value:
"{Number1: 1, Number2: 2}"

[5.009] SEND
<Text Generator> client sends message to topic
Generated Value:
"{Text: OFF}"

[5.01] SEND
<Number & Text Generator> client sends message to topic
Mix Generated Values:
"{Number: 0, Text: OFF}"

[5.012] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Generated Value:
"{Number1: 1, Number2: 2}"

[5.013] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Generated Value:
"{Text: OFF}"

[5.013] GET
<Data Viewer> client gets message from topic
Mix Generated Values:
"{Number: 0, Text: OFF}"
```

Figure 7: Output Data in the Specified File

Messages are grouped into smaller packets. The first line of each packet shows the elapsed time since the start of the simulation and the message type. The "SEND" type means the

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client sent a message to the given topic, while the "GET" type means the client received a message on a subscribed topic. From the second line onward, details about the client and topic related to the event are displayed. The last line contains the message content.